

INFLATION PROCESSES AND ANTI-INFLATION POLICY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17706933>

Abstract. This article inflation processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, their main causes, and the essence of the anti-inflation policy. Based on statistical data for the period between 2020 and 2025, the article analyzes the changing trends in the inflation rate. Furthermore, it evaluates the effectiveness of the monetary and fiscal policy measures being conducted by the Central Bank and the government.

Keywords: inflation, anti-inflation policy, monetary policy, fiscal policy, price stability, economic growth.

Introduction. Inflation is one of the most important macroeconomic indicators, and its level directly impacts ensuring economic stability and increasing social welfare in the country. In recent years, Uzbekistan has implemented wide-ranging reforms aimed at reducing inflation, improving monetary-credit policy, and maintaining the stability of the national currency. The purpose of this article is to analyze the course of inflation processes in Uzbekistan and to evaluate the anti-inflation policy being pursued.

Inflation is the rise in the prices of goods and services, i.e., the decrease in the purchasing power of money. Today, inflation is one of the key indicators affecting economic stability, living standards, and the business environment. While moderate inflation can aid economic growth, its excessive increase or decrease can lead to economic stagnation. Controlling the inflation rate is one of the primary tasks of Central Banks, through which a balance between economic development and monetary-credit policy is ensured. For the population, inflation affects the standard of living and purchasing power, and for entrepreneurs, it is crucial in financial planning. Therefore, inflation is a critical strategic factor for the country's economy. The term "inflation" was first introduced into economic circulation in 1864 by the American economist A. Delmar, which occurred because the US Federal government, during the country's civil war from 1861-1865, put a very large amount of paper money into circulation to cover the state's expenses. In short, inflation, as a form of violation of the laws of money circulation, signifies a disruption of macroeconomic balance, a disproportion between demand and supply. Inflation (from the Latin *inflatio* - swelling, expansion, distension) is a sustained increase in the average (general) level of prices in the country over a certain period, and a long-term decrease in the purchasing power of money as a result of a rise in the general price level. This, in turn, leads to the devaluation of the country's national currency or monetary unit. In this context, the devaluation of money means that the quantity of certain goods and services that can be purchased at a certain price will be lower at that same price after some time.

Demand-pull inflation occurs when there is a sharp increase in aggregate demand in the economy, which can no longer be satisfied by the real volume of production. Excess demand leads to a rise in prices. As prices rise, the opportunity to increase profits arises. Producers then expand production, hire additional labor, the unemployment rate falls, and as a result, wages

rise, which in turn leads to a further increase in demand and a rise in prices. In this case, there can be two initial situations: a rise in wages (due to the demands of trade unions or workers) or an increase in the cost of raw materials and fuel (due to rising import prices, changes in extraction conditions, increased transport costs, etc.), which results in cost-push inflation. Even if aggregate demand in the market is not excessive, a decrease in the supply of goods due to rising production costs can occur. This, in turn, leads to a rise in prices and subsequently to a new turn of inflation. In practice, it is very difficult to distinguish between the two types of inflation. However, it is important to know which type of inflation causes inflationary price growth. In many developed countries, cost-push inflation has a self-regulating property: if income increases and prices rise, then the production and supply of goods gradually decrease, which in turn contains the rise in production costs. A combination of demand-pull and cost-push inflation is reflected in the inflationary spiral, where the growing inflationary expectations of economic agents act as a transmission mechanism. If the Central Bank and the government cannot manage inflationary expectations, the "wages-prices" movement that forms the basis of the spiral can lead to hyperinflation. In general, hyperinflation is uncontrollable. Price control instruments and usual functional relationships cease to work. Printing presses operate at full capacity, unprecedented speculation begins. Production gets out of control. Special measures are needed to curb hyperinflation. However, there is no single instruction on what these measures should be.

Today, there is a popular belief that inflation at any level has a negative aspect, but in reality, not any level of inflation is harmful to the economy. Low, stable inflation for economic growth is a natural process. Low-level inflation can stimulate economic growth by creating additional demand in the economy. The complete absence of inflation, however, can slow down the economy's growth rate. Galloping inflation can lead to high inflation in the future, derailing the economy. From this point of view, low, stable inflation is considered positive. The relative change in the average (general) level of prices is called the inflation rate (the rate of price growth). In macroeconomic models, the inflation rate can be expressed as follows:

$$\pi = \frac{P - P_{-1}}{P_{-1}} \times 100\%$$

Where:

π – annual inflation rate;

P – current year's price index;

P-1 – previous year's price index.

The Consumer Price Index (CPI) reflects the average change in the general price level of a certain set of goods and services, based on the demand of households. This general indicator is calculated taking into account the price changes for each good and service in the consumer basket. The following formula is used to determine the inflation rate using the CPI:

$$\text{Inflation rate in year N} = \frac{\text{CPI in year N} - \text{CPI in year N-1}}{\text{CPI in year N-1}} \times 100\%$$

The GDP deflator can also be used to determine the inflation rate. The GDP deflator is an index that reflects the dynamics of the change in the average price of all goods and services produced in the country relative to a base period. The deflator is calculated using the following formula: Inflation rate in year N = (Deflator in year N - Deflator in year N-1) / (Deflator in year N-1) × 100%

An average household does not consume all goods and services produced in the economy. Therefore, the GDP deflator is not a suitable indicator for measuring household inflation. Currently, inflation targeting is one of the most popular methods of conducting monetary policy, used in over 40 countries worldwide. The word "target" comes from English and means "goal" or "objective." In an inflation targeting regime, a target inflation rate is set. To achieve this inflation target, the mechanisms of monetary policy are gradually transitioned to this regime, and they are used as an effective instrument to reduce inflation. In turn, the application of this regime can create additional conditions for strong and stable economic growth in the medium term by ensuring price stability. At the same time, the Central Bank achieves this by determining the most appropriate inflation target, applying monetary policy instruments to it, regularly analyzing economic development, and widely publicizing monetary policy plans.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 18, 2019, PF-5877 "On Improving Monetary Policy through a Gradual Transition to an Inflation Targeting Regime," it was determined that the Central Bank of Uzbekistan would gradually transition to an inflation targeting regime starting January 1, 2020. This decree planned to set an inflation target of 10% by 2021 and a constant inflation target of 5% by 2023. According to data from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the inflation rate in our country in 2023 was 8.77%. This is the lowest figure since 2016. In the "Main Directions of Monetary Policy for 2023 and the period 2024-2025" published by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022, the target inflation rate to be achieved in our country was set at 5%. Trends in the economy and the external situation indicate that the period for achieving the target will be in the second half of 2024.

In the last five-year period, the course of inflation processes in the economy of Uzbekistan has gone through its own unique stages. According to Central Bank data, the inflation rate is gradually decreasing in the period from 2020 to 2025. This process is related to the strict monetary policy being pursued in the country, strengthening fiscal discipline, and the consolidation of market mechanisms.

Table 1. Inflation Rate in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2025 (%)

Year	Inflation Rate (%)	Comment
2020	11.1	High level under the influence of the pandemic
2021	10.9	Beginning of the decrease in price pressure
2022	12.3	External shocks and rising energy prices
2023	9.2	Tightening of monetary policy
2024	8.4	Stabilization period
2025	7.8	Inflation decline phase – the lowest indicator

As can be seen from the table, the inflation rate decreased from 11.1% to 7.8% between 2020 and 2025. This situation is the result of the strict monetary policy conducted by the Central Bank to reduce inflation and the government's measures to optimize budget expenditures.

Additionally, factors such as a decrease in import dependency, the expansion of local production, and the transition to alternative energy sources played an important role in the course of inflation. As a result of stabilized population expectations and an expansion in the supply of the consumer market, the pace of price growth slowed down.

Anti-Inflation Policy. The anti-inflation policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is being pursued in three main directions:

- 1) monetary policy;
- 2) fiscal policy;
- 3) institutional reforms.

Within the framework of monetary policy, the Central Bank has kept the base interest rate at 14%, thereby controlling the growth of the money supply by limiting excess liquidity. The bank is analyzing the volume and direction of credit in the banking system and taking measures to soften inflationary pressure.

In terms of fiscal policy, measures were implemented to reduce pressure on the domestic market by increasing the efficiency of state expenditures, reducing the budget deficit, and simplifying tax policy. In 2024–2025, the share of state expenditures in GDP decreased from 26% to 22%.

Furthermore, measures implemented by the government in the energy sector reform, ensuring food security, and developing domestic competition have had a positive impact on the process of reducing inflation.

Conclusion. The course of inflation processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan over the last five years shows that the rate of price growth is gradually decreasing. This indicates the strengthening of macroeconomic stability in the economy. Through the anti-inflation policy, the improvement of monetary-credit instruments, the strengthening of fiscal discipline, and the development of production are emerging as important factors. In the future, to stabilize inflation at the 5% level, it is necessary to reduce import dependency, direct investments to the production sectors, and consistently liberalize monetary policy.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Elov, O. K. (2023). Human Resource Information Systems Developing Of Organization. Экономика и социум, (6-1 (109)), 121-124.
2. Elov, O., & Kuvandikova, B. (2025). INTERNATIONAL MODELS OF MANAGEMENT: BY NAVOIY REGION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(32), 141-146.
3. Elov, O., Niyatova, I., & Toshtemirova, M. (2025). FACTORS OF MANAGING AND RESOLVING CONFLICTS: THE CASE OF NAVOI REGION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(31), 123-128.
4. Elov, O. (2025). REGISTRATION OF PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: IN THE CONTEXT OF NAVOIY REGION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(30), 100-108.

5. Elov, O., & Xidirova, S. (2025). COMPARATIVE MANAGEMENT MODELS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(30), 95-99.
6. Elov, O., & Baxtiyorova, G. (2025). THE ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE ECONOMY: THE CASE OF NAVOI REGION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(30), 90-94.
7. Elov, O., & Hasanova, E. (2025). THE ROLE OF TAXES IN ECONOMIC MANAGEMENT AND THEIR PRACTICAL ASPECTS IN THE NAVOI REGION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(29), 162-166.
8. Komilovich, E. O., & Buriboyeva, S. (2025). THE PURPOSE AND TASKS OF DEVELOPING SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES: THE CASE OF NAVOIY REGION. Modern American Journal of Business, Economics, and Entrepreneurship, 1(2), 291-299.
9. Elov, O., & Bobojonov, D. (2025). STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING QUALITY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(2), 47-51.
10. Elov, O., & Yoqubova, S. (2025). THE PRACTICE OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(2), 15-20.
11. Elov, O., & Sodiqova, O. (2025). ELECTRONIC SYSTEM FOR MONITORING AND EVALUATING EDUCATION QUALITY. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(2), 38-42.
12. Elov, O., & Ibragimova, I. (2025). QUALITY ASSESSMENT AND MONITORING SYSTEMS. Современные подходы и новые исследования в современной науке, 4(1), 48-53.
13. Elov, O., & Qudratova, S. (2025). ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS OF TEACHING QUALITY. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(1), 137-141.
14. Elov, O., & Baxtiyorova, G. (2025). MODERN ASSESSMENT METHODS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 4(1), 165-170.
15. Latipov N. Shaharlar va ularning ekologik muhit bilan bog'liqligi. Scienceweb academic papers collection. 2022.
16. Латипов, Н. Ф. (2017). Locality and factors affecting the population. Наука и мир, 1(11), 74-75.
17. Komilova, N. K., & Latipov, N. F. (2022). FACTORS AFFECTING THE ECOLOGICAL STATUS OF INDUSTRIALIZED CITIES AND MEASURES TO MONITOR THEM (ON THE EXAMPLE OF NAVOI REGION). Экономика и социум, (2-2 (93)), 199-206.
18. Latipov, N. (2022). УРБОЭКОЛОГИЯ-ГЕОГРАФИЯ ВА ЭКОЛОГИЯНИНГ ФАНЛАРАРО СИНТЕЗИ. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
19. Latipov, N. (2022). НАВОЙ ВИЛОЯТИ МАЪМУРИЙ БИРЛИКЛАРИ ЭКОЛОГИК ҲОЛАТИ ТАСНИФИ ВА АҲОЛИ САЛОМАТЛИГИГА ТАЪСИР ЭТУВЧИ ОМИЛЛАР. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
20. Kalonov, B. H., & Latipov, N. F. (2013). Geographical peculiarities of population in Navoi region. SCIENCE AND WORLD, 79.
21. Latipov, N. (2022). НАВОЙ ВИЛОЯТИДА АХ. ОЛИ САЛОМАТЛИГИГА ЭКОЛОГИЯНИНГ ТАЪСИРИ.

22. Latipov, N. F. (2024). THE PROCESS OF URBANIZATION AND ITS CORRELATION WITH THE ECOLOGICAL CIRCUMSTANCE. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 4), 343-352.
23. LATIPOV, N. (2024). THE ESTABLISHMENT AND STRUCTURE OF THE CITIES OF THE NAVOI REGION. *News of the NUUZ*, 3(3.1. 1), 237-240.
24. Латипов, Н. Ф. (2018). International migration tours and works. *Наука и мир*, (8), 108-110.
25. КОМИЛОВА, N., & LATIPOV, N. ЭКОНОМИКА И СОЦИУМ. ЭКОНОМИКА, 161-165.
26. Latipov, N. F. (2025). THE SOCIO-GEOGRAPHICAL FACTORS INFLUENCING ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS AND PUBLIC HEALTH IN INDUSTRIALISED CITIES. *Экономика и социум*, (6-2 (133)), 472-475.
27. Faxriddin o'g'li, L. N. (2023). ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY AND HEALTH PROBLEMS IN NAVOI PROVINCE CITIES. NEW INTEGRATIONS OF MODERN EDUCATION IN UNIVERSITIES, 87.
28. Latipov, N. F. (2023). ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC HEALTH AS THE MOST IMPORTANT FACTOR AFFECTING URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY.(IN THE CASE OF THE NAVOI REGION). *Экономика и социум*, (11 (114)-2), 202-208.
29. Faxriddin O'g'li, L. N. (2022, November). INDICATORS OF URBAN ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT AND CRITERIA FOR THEIR SELECTION. In *The 7th International scientific and practical conference "Innovative areas of solving problems of science and practice"*(November 08–11, 2022) Oslo, Norway. International Science Group. 2022. 700 p. (p. 153).
30. Karshiboevna, K. N., & Faxriddin, L. N. (2022). Mini-review article Factors affecting the ecological status of industrialized cities and measures to monitor them. *nutrition*, 5, 0.